

Effect of certain factors on hair quality attributes in Indian dromedary camel managed in an organised farm

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ABSTRACT

Hair samples (188) collected from 4 important body sites of 47 Indian dromedary camels belonging to 3 age groups (1, 4 and 8 year) and from 3 breeds (Bikaneri, Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi) were analysed for quality attributes of hair. The hair samples taken from shoulder, mid, hump, and neck region of individual camel were compared for staple length, hair diameter and hair types, viz. pure, hetro, hairy and kemp. The data were analysed using mixed mode least square and maximum likely hood programme to study the factors like breed, sex, site and age influencing hair quality attributes. The mean staple length varied from 4.65 ± 0.42 cm to 6.68 ± 0.21 cm. The body sites and age significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced the staple length whereas sex had a nonsignificant effect. The Bikaneri camel showed minimum mean hair diameter followed by Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi breeds. The least square analysis indicated significant ($P < 0.01$) effect of all factors, viz. breed, sex, site and age on hair diameter. The pure type had minimum hair diameter followed by hetro hairy and kemp in all 3 breeds, both sex, in all age groups and also in all body sites of camel. The factors like breed and age had significant ($P < 0.01$) effect on all types of hair whereas site significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced pure, hetro and hairy types. The nonsignificant effect of sex on kemp type was also observed. The mid side of body region indicated maximum percentage of pure hair whereas neck region had maximum kemp hair. The breed and age factor affected significantly ($P < 0.01$) all hair types. The sex had nonsignificant effect on hetro, hairy, kemp but significant effect on pure type. The body site had a significant effect on kemp hair.

Key words: Camel hair, Dromedary camel, Hair quality attributes

The camel hair is used in village cottage industry for preparation of common utility items, viz. blankets, bags, mattress, ropes and floor rugs. It is widely used in rural cottage industry of Rajasthan and Gujarat for preparation of various items (Sahani and Khanna 1993). The preliminary results of camel hair blends with wool, silk waste and polyester have shown encouraging results (Gupta *et al.* 1997, 1989). Blended products may also be prepared with sheep wool, goat hair and cotton. Patni and Dhillon (1988) reported that it is worth while to blend camel hair with polyester, wool or silk waste. The camel hair is being utilized in India since ancient times. It has been estimated that a camel hair fabric of 620 g weight will be as warm as a pure wool fabric of 900 g weight (Khanna and Rai 1991).

The hair is spun by camel keepers by using traditional simple techniques. The coarse variety is spun by hand dheyria. The other method of spinning fine quality camel hair is by hand charkas. In the recent times machine spinning is

becoming popular for carpets, *dumese* clothing. The camel hair is stronger and warmer as compared to wool (Khanna and Rai 1990). The handicraft articles made up of camel hair, provide work to women in the field of grading of hair, tops preparation, spinning of wool, weaving, embroidery with 100% speciality hair and blending with sheep wool, goat hair, cotton and other products. The camel hair and its products can be an important source of additional income for camel keeper. The main body sites of hair coverage in the dromedary camels are shoulder, mid portion of body, neck and hump regions. The hair of dromedary camels are durable, strong and have low conductivity (Muksa 1981). Therefore analysis of hair quality characteristics of various breeds, body-sites of camel etc. is of great importance in exploiting the hair production potential and quality of hair for its future utility as pure camel hair as well as blends with other animal fibres, synthetic waste fibres and its uses in the rural cottage industry. Thus the present investigation was undertaken as an attempt to explore the different factors influencing hair quality attributes in Indian dromedary camel managed in an organised farm and there can be help full in effective utilization of camel hair in the form of blends.

Table 1. Least square mean \pm SE values for hair quality attributes of Indian dromedary camels

	Breed			Sex		Site				Age (years)			Overall
	Bikaneri	Jaisalmeri	Kachchhi	Male	Female	Shoulder	Mid	Hump	Neck	1	4	8	
Staple length (cm)	6.68 ^a \pm 0.21 (93)	6.16 ^b \pm 0.24 (71)	4.65 ^c \pm 0.42 (24)	5.60 ^d \pm 0.24 (88)	6.00 ^d \pm 0.21 (100)	4.87 ^e \pm 0.30 (47)	4.41 ^f \pm 0.30 (47)	10.14 ^g \pm 0.30 (47)	3.90 ^h \pm 0.30 (47)	5.47 ⁱ \pm 0.28 (68)	6.49 ^j \pm 0.27 (60)	5.54 ^k \pm 0.26 (60)	5.83 ^l \pm 0.17 (188)
Hair diameter (μ)	32.76 ^a \pm 0.52 (93)	35.52 ^b \pm 0.59 (71)	38.19 ^c \pm 1.07 (24)	34.05 ^d \pm 0.59 (88)	36.93 ^e \pm 0.55 (100)	34.49 ^f \pm 0.76 (47)	32.98 ^g \pm 0.76 (47)	39.02 ^h \pm 0.76 (47)	35.48 ⁱ \pm 0.77 (47)	26.05 ^j \pm 0.72 (68)	31.72 ^k \pm 0.68 (60)	48.70 ^l \pm 0.66 (60)	35.49 ^m \pm 0.44 (188)
Pure diameter (μ)	24.01 ^a \pm 0.47 (93)	27.30 ^b \pm 0.54 (71)	33.41 ^c \pm 0.97 (24)	24.41 ^d \pm 0.54 (88)	30.06 ^e \pm 0.50 (100)	27.08 ^f \pm 0.69 (47)	26.37 ^g \pm 0.69 (47)	30.92 ^h \pm 0.69 (47)	27.78 ⁱ \pm 0.69 (47)	22.12 ^j \pm 0.365 (68)	25.16 ^k \pm 0.62 (60)	37.43 ^l \pm 0.60 (60)	28.24 ^m \pm 0.39 (188)
Hetro diameter (μ)	31.13 ^a \pm 0.54 (93)	33.20 ^b \pm 0.61 (71)	38.76 ^c \pm 1.10 (24)	32.47 ^d \pm 0.61 (88)	36.25 ^e \pm 0.56 (100)	33.37 ^f \pm 0.79 (47)	31.50 ^g \pm 0.79 (47)	37.84 ^h \pm 0.79 (47)	34.75 ⁱ \pm 0.79 (47)	26.28 ^j \pm 0.74 (68)	31.15 ^k \pm 0.70 (60)	45.66 ^l \pm 0.68 (60)	34.36 ^m \pm 0.44 (188)
Hairy diameter (μ)	42.50 ^a \pm 0.74 (93)	48.00 ^b \pm 0.83 (71)	50.24 ^c \pm 1.50 (24)	46.03 ^d \pm 0.83 (88)	47.80 ^e \pm 0.77 (100)	46.34 ^f \pm 1.07 (47)	44.85 ^g \pm 1.07 (47)	48.27 ^h \pm 1.08 (47)	48.20 ⁱ \pm 1.07 (47)	35.74 ^j \pm 1.01 (68)	45.48 ^k \pm 0.96 (60)	59.52 ^l \pm 0.93 (60)	46.91 ^m \pm 0.61 (188)
Kemp diameter (μ)	72.33 ^a \pm 2.40 (93)	39.08 ^b \pm 2.71 (71)	44.89 ^c \pm 4.87 (24)	51.25 ^d \pm 2.71 (88)	52.95 ^e \pm 2.50 (100)	52.73 ^f \pm 3.49 (47)	48.20 ^g \pm 3.49 (47)	56.36 ^h \pm 3.49 (47)	51.12 ⁱ \pm 3.49 (47)	39.19 ^j \pm 3.28 (68)	33.53 ^k \pm 3.12 (60)	83.57 ^l \pm 3.01 (60)	52.10 ^m \pm 1.98 (188)

Similar superscripts of a quality parameter do not differ significantly from each other.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The hair samples collected from 47 camels (*Camelus dromedarius*) Bikaneri, Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi breeds belonging to the NRC on Camel, Bikaner, were micro-analysed. All the camels were managed under semi-intensive system of management and were daily sent for grazing/browsing for about 6 hr and offered dry fodder in the evening. The camel belonged to different age groups, viz. 1-year (17 camel calves), 4-year (15 camels), and adults 8-year aged (15 camels). The hair samples of annual clip were collected from shoulder, mid-side, hump and neck region during the last week of March. The samples were analysed for hair diameter, staple length and types of hair, viz. pure, hetro, hairy and kemp. The staple length was measured before washing of samples. The hair samples were washed thoroughly in petrol, dried for overnight and further washed for evaluating the different parameters. The individual samples were mixed thoroughly to prepare a representative sample and then slides were prepared after proper sectioning. The slides were examined under the microscope at 500 \times magnification, for measuring diameter and assessing the hair types based on medulation percentage. In each slide 300 observations were recorded to minimise the error. The data were classified according to breed, sex, site and age effects and then analysed using mixed model least square and maximum likelihood computer programme (Harvey 1987).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The least square mean \pm SE value for hair quality attributes

of Indian dromedary camels are presented in Table 1. The highest staple length was found in Bikaneri breed followed by Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi breed. Yadav *et al.* (2000) reported that young Bikaneri camels indicated higher staple length as compared to young Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi camel. The hump region of all camel breeds possessed the hair with the longest staple length followed by shoulder, mid-side whereas neck region had the smallest hair staple length. Similar trend of observatin in young camel was reported by Sahani *et al.* (1998). The 4-year aged group had maximum staple length as compared to longer and adult (8 years) aged group of camel. The overall staple length of Indian dromedary camel was found to be 5.83 \pm 0.17 cm. The factors like breed, body sites and age significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced the staple length whereas sex factors had nonsignificant effect. The mean hair diameter of Bikaneri breed was minimum followed by Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi. Gupta *et al.* (1989) found that there is large variability in mean fibre diameter of camel hair. The mean hair diameter of male camel was lesser than that of female camel. The mid site of body region had lowest hair diameter followed by shoulder and neck whereas hump region had the highest diameter. The results are consistent with the observation reported by Sahani *et al.* (1998). The hair diameter gradually increased according to advancement of age. Minimum diameter was found in 1-year and maximum was in 8-year adult group of camel. The least square analysis indicated significant ($P < 0.01$) effect of all factors, viz. breed, sex, site and age on hair diameter.

The mean hair diameter for pure, hetro, hairy and kemp were also estimated and compared among the breed, sex, site

Table 2. Least square mean \pm SE values for different composition of hair

Breed	Hair types (%)			
	Pure	Hetro	Hairy	Kemp
Bikaneri	36.60 ^a \pm 0.63(93)	39.68 ^a \pm 0.53(93)	20.49 ^a \pm 0.57(93)	3.19 ^a \pm 0.16(93)
Jaisalmeri	36.31 ^b \pm 0.71(71)	38.41 ^b \pm 0.60(71)	23.85 ^b \pm 0.64(71)	1.25 ^b \pm 0.18(71)
Kachchhi	40.68 ^c \pm 1.28 (24)	42.19 ^c \pm 1.08 (24)	14.99 ^c \pm 1.15(24)	2.08 ^c \pm 0.34(24)
Sex				
Male	36.76 ^a \pm 0.71(88)	40.67 ^a \pm 0.68(88)	20.36 ^a \pm 0.64(88)	2.10 ^a \pm 0.18(88)
Female	38.97 ^b \pm 0.65(100)	39.52 ^b \pm 0.56(100)	19.19 ^b \pm 0.59(100)	2.25 ^b \pm 0.17(100)
Site				
Shoulder	37.71 ^a \pm 0.91(47)	40.03 ^a \pm 0.78(47)	20.55 ^f \pm 0.82(47)	1.72 ^a \pm 0.24(47)
Mid	39.09 ^a \pm 0.91(47)	38.57 ^a \pm 0.78(47)	20.41 ^f \pm 0.82(47)	1.88 ^b \pm 0.24(47)
Hump	36.89 ^a \pm 0.91(47)	40.89 ^a \pm 0.78(47)	19.46 ^f \pm 0.83(47)	2.44 ^a \pm 0.24(47)
Neck	37.76 ^a \pm 0.91(47)	40.89 ^a \pm 0.78(47)	18.68 ^f \pm 0.82(47)	2.65 ^a \pm 0.24(47)
Age				
1 year	45.70 ^d \pm 0.86(68)	35.20 ^f \pm 0.73(68)	16.46 ^e \pm 0.77(68)	2.60 ^d \pm 0.22(68)
4 year	38.98 ^c \pm 0.82(60)	41.22 ^e \pm 0.69(60)	18.18 ^b \pm 0.74(60)	1.40 ^e \pm 0.21 (60)
8 year	28.90 ^f \pm 0.79(60)	43.86 ^b \pm 0.67(60)	24.68 ^a \pm 0.71(60)	2.51 ^b \pm 0.21(60)
Overall	37.86 \pm 0.52 (188)	40.09 \pm 0.44 (188)	19.77 \pm 0.47(188)	2.17 \pm 0.13(188)

Similar superscripts of a quality parameter do not differ significantly from each other.

and age group of camel. The result revealed that the pure had minimum hair diameter followed by hetro, hairy and kemp in all the 3 breeds. The similar trend was observed in both sexes in all age groups and at 4 sites of body region of camel. The Bikaneri breed showed minimum diameter of all types of hair followed by Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi camel. The male had lesser hair diameter than that of female camel for all types of hair. The ascending order of mean diameter in all types of hair were mid-site, shoulder, neck and hump region. As the age of camel increased the diameter of all the types of hair increased. The overall hair diameter (μ) were 28.24 ± 0.39 , 34.36 ± 0.44 , 46.91 ± 0.61 , 52.10 ± 1.98 for pure, hetro, hairy and kemp hair respectively. The factors like breed and age had significant ($P < 0.01$) effect on all types whereas site significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced pure, hetro and hairy types but nonsignificant for kemp.

The least square mean \pm SE value for different composition of hair are revealed in the Table 2. The overall percentage of hair types, pure, hetro, hairy and kemp was 37.86, 40.09, 19.77 and 2.17 respectively. The young age group (1-year) showed maximum pure types (45.70%) followed by 4-year and 8-year age. The purity of hair gradually reduced as the camel becomes aged whereas adult age group content maximum hetro type (43.86%). The mid-site of body region of Indian dromedary camel showed maximum percentage of pure hair whereas neck region had maximum kemp hair.

The least square analysis for percentage of hair types indicated that breed and age factor affect significantly ($P < 0.01$). The sex factor had nonsignificant effect on hetro, hairy, kemp, but significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on pure type. The body site was having a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on kemp type.

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